

POLITICAL SCIENCES

POSITIVE TRANSFORMATION OF THE CYPRUS CONFLICT AND PEACEBUILDING PERSPECTIVE IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

The purpose of our paper is to demonstrate the contemporary conflict resolution strategy that is currently thought to be the most effective, specifically conflict transformation which refers to reestablishing trust and reconciliation between the opposing parties, primarily on a human level and peacebuilding which refers to eradicating all signs of conflict. In terms of positive transformation of the conflict and peacebuilding, the Cyprus case is considered one of the most visible examples. In our opinion, the main strategy for resolving the Georgian-Abkhazian and Georgian-Ossetian conflicts is through positive transformation of the conflict.

Keywords: Conflict Transformation, Peacebuilding, Cyprus, European Union, Georgia.

Introduction

In the last fifty years, the study of conflicts has acquired a topical character. At the end of the 20th century, a new scientific approach to the study of conflicts was formed, which included the study of conflict transformation and peacebuilding. Although the disciplines of conflict studies and peace studies serve the same purpose, there is one key difference between them: as a result of studying the conflict, it is possible to resolve it, but this does not guarantee peace. The essence of peacebuilding is well illustrated by the following idea: "There is no peace without reconciliation; there is no reconciliation without dialogue; dialogue is the recognition of each other's opinion" [11.8].

Positive transformation of the conflict is a necessary stage for achieving peace. American scientist, theoretician, and one of the founders of peacebuilding as a scientific direction, John Paul Lederach, prefers to focus only on conflict resolution and the peacebuilding process and presents it as a period of long-term transformations from armed conflict to peace. He considers the establishment of healthy relations between the conflicting parties to be the starting point of conflict transformation. According to John Paul Lederach, the conflict resolution process focuses directly on the content of the conflict and on the relationship where the crisis takes place. The transformation of the conflict provides a direct presentation of the problem and a wide opportunity to study and understand the system of tense relations and the reasons that created the crisis. However, the theory implies a multidimensional approach to conflict, which includes restoring trust for reconciliation at all levels, be they social, political, psychological, or emotional. Narrow approaches to conflict resolution may solve problems but miss the greater potential of constructive, beneficial changes [7]. John Paul Lederach's transformative peacebuilding theory argues that especially most ethnic conflicts cannot be finally resolved if the society divided by the conflict does not change its approach to the conflict itself and trust and

readiness for reconciliation do not emerge. As proof of this, we quote Abraham Lincoln's opinion that "the best way to destroy an enemy is to make him a friend".

The Cyprus Conflict

In terms of positive transformation of the conflict and peacebuilding, the Cyprus issue is considered one of the most visible examples. The roots of the Cyprus conflict can be traced back to the early period, although in modern terms, the problem began when the island was granted independence in 1960 after 82 years of British colonial rule. The constitutional agreement created to balance Greek and Turkish Cypriot relations lasted only three years. In 1963, the controversy erupted with new force. In March 1964, the UN Security Council decided to establish a peacekeeping force on the island. A mediator was also appointed to help both sides reach a political agreement. In July 1974, a coup d'état took place in Nicosia with the support of the Athens junta. Extremist forces that seized power announced "enosis", which meant the unification of Cyprus with Greece. Considering the threat that Greece could annex the island, the Turkish government, based on the guarantee agreement, carried out a military intervention on the island. The Turkish army was able to capture 36 percent of the island's territory. The result for the Greek Cypriots was catastrophic. 160,000 people, about a third of the Greek Cypriot population, left their homes, and the most economically productive areas of the island came under Turkish occupation. Soon after, the Turkish Cypriot community moved from areas under the control of the Greek Cypriot government to Northern Cyprus. In this way, Cyprus was divided into two mutually resentful communities, which began to live separately [6]. The "green zone" established by the United Nations in Nicosia, which is still a kind of buffer zone, has become a symbol of the island's physical and political disconnection.

The role of international organizations in the Cyprus conflict resolution

Naturally, there was a response to the mentioned events at the international level. In November 1974, the UN General Assembly adopted Resolution (#3212 (XXIX)), according to which the Assembly "urged the speedy withdrawal of all foreign armed forces and foreign military presence personnel from the Republic of Cyprus and the cessation of all foreign interference in its affairs" [4]. In addition, the US Congress imposed sanctions on Turkey, including an arms embargo.

In fact, after the division of the island in 1974, the issue of conflict resolution entered a difficult phase, which was crowned with an absolutely negative result: in 1983, amid fruitless negotiations, Turkish Cypriot leaders issued a unilateral declaration of independence and established the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus, which was recognized only by Turkey, although this fact made the situation worse. The declaration of Turkish Cypriot independence in 1983 was the result of decades of effort from both internal and external factors [5.169].

Despite the efforts and involvement of the UN and European structures, it was not possible to restore trust and reconciliation between the conflict's participants. They chose a different way of life: Northern Cyprus was closed off and tied to Turkey's politics and economy, while Greek Cypriots took a course toward Western-style country-building and the European Union.

As time passed and efforts to end the conflict on the island failed, there was less and less chance of resolving the Cyprus issue.

The most interesting phase of the peacebuilding process in Cyprus began in 2003. In 2002, UN Secretary General Kofi Annan presented the Peace Initiative and Plan, which meant the creation of a federation of two equal entities. Greek Cypriots expressed doubt and assumed that, on the basis of such a state arrangement, more political and legal grounds for secession and independence would be created on the Turkish side in the future. Besides that, the Greek community was in an unfavorable position from an economic point of view because it had to finance 95 percent of all the structures of the United Cyprus [8.504]. In addition, there were still unacceptable issues for the Greek Cypriots. At the same time, the Greek part of Cyprus expected to join the European Union, which gave it serious expectations for strengthening its position (on May 1, 2004, the Republic of Cyprus became a member of the European Union). For Turkish Cypriots, the main attraction was the high standard of living and economic strength of the Greeks, which would become even more visible after joining the European Union. All of the aforementioned factors played a role, and in a referendum held on April 24, 2004, on both sides of Cyprus regarding the adoption of Kofi Annan's plan, 65% of Turks supported it, while 76% of Greeks opposed it. This rejection of the plan among Greek Cypriots was the result of a general perception that the Annan plan was unbalanced and unfair to Greek Cypriots [1.5].

Despite the failure of the referendum, during this period the foundations were laid for a positive transformation of the conflict in Cyprus, which is as follows:

Greek Cypriots were able to relocate north after the Northern Cypriot administration opened the Green Line in 2003. In just a few days, the Greek side of Cyprus responded with the same step. From the first day, active traffic started in both directions. What was once a dividing line is now a starting point for restoring mutual trust and reconciliation.

The European Union expressed great support for the rapprochement of the Turkish and Greek Cypriot communities. One of its fundamental principles is the free movement of people, goods, and services among member states, which naturally affected Cyprus as well. Since 2004, Green Line regulations have been developed to facilitate people-to-people contacts and trade in Cyprus.

The border is not part of the EU's external borders. The conditions under which people and goods may cross this line from areas not under government control into areas under government control are outlined in Council Regulation 866/2004 ("Green Line Regulation") [2]. The personal rights of Turkish Cypriots as citizens of the EU are unaffected by the fact that the non-government-controlled areas are outside the EU's customs and fiscal territory.

The European Union has also provided funding for a number of initiatives to promote communication and collaboration between the two Cypriot communities. These initiatives help to rebuild trust between the parties and are both economically and socially significant.

EU assistance aims to strengthen ties between the Turkish and Greek Cypriot populations in order to facilitate reunification. It is noteworthy and important that the European Commission has established an informal working group on Halloumi/Hellim. The group shall bring about an exchange of information as well as the sharing of experience and good practices among stakeholders relating to their participation in the PDO scheme for Halloumi/Hellim and will review the functioning of the inspection system for Halloumi/Hellim. The group shall be composed of up to ten members of whom an equal number shall be drawn from the Greek Cypriot community and from the Turkish Cypriot community. Members shall be individuals appointed to represent a common interest, such as representatives of Chambers of Commerce, representatives of farmers' organizations or representatives of dairies involved in the production of Halloumi/Hellim, representatives of relevant professional interests and representatives of civil society organizations. The group will meet periodically. On September 23, 2022, the Commission's Informal Working Group on Halloumi/Hellim held its inaugural meeting[10].

The opening of the Green Line has brought positive results in many directions. As a result of direct relations, people in both North and South believed that dialogue was possible; there was a willingness to forgive; and there was more economic cooperation. The international political situation has changed. Greece and Turkey are no longer allowed to antagonize. Civil society organizations learn to use diplomatic language and tactics [8]. The ice has been broken, building confidence, and the peace process has entered an active phase at the human level, which will certainly lead to

successful political negotiations, although agreement at this level has not yet been reached and the Cyprus problem remains unresolved.

The case of Bosnia and Herzegovina: parallel

Let's briefly discuss the situation in Bosnia and Herzegovina, where the parties - Bosniaks, Croats, and Serbs - put an end to the armed conflict in 1995 on the basis of the Dayton Agreement. With the help of international actors, particularly the United States of America's involvement, they were able to negotiate and begin living together in a state. It should be noted that Bosnia and Herzegovina's post-conflict state organization and management are marked by precedent-setting decisions. The most important decision was the establishment of a presidium made up of three presidents from each ethnic group, which confirmed a political balance. We believe that from this perspective, it may be viewed as an effective model for conflict resolution at this level [3.34]. However, despite having lived together for 25 years, they are still at odds. Conflict between ethnic groups prevents people from living in peace. A peaceful life is not necessarily correlated with the absence of war, as demonstrated by the fact that the conflict in Bosnia and Herzegovina has been resolved. However, because of the bloody conflict that broke out immediately after Yugoslavia's dissolution, the stage of trust-building or constructive conflict transformation was missed, which ultimately turned the unity mandated by outside forces into a phony peace.

Conclusion

The aim of our work was to show the modern approach, which is considered the most successful today in terms of the final management of conflicts. These are conflict transformation, which implies the restoration of trust and reconciliation between the conflicting parties mainly at the human level, and peacebuilding, which means reducing all indicators of conflict to zero. Even though each ethnic-political conflict is unique, we believe that positive transformation of the conflict always brings a successful outcome because it is much easier to live with people you trust.

In our opinion, the main strategy for resolving the Georgian-Abkhazian and Georgian-Ossetian conflicts is through positive transformation of the conflict. The transformation of ethno-political conflicts is a long and complex process. In order to be prepared to use the "window of opportunities" in the necessary historical period and avoid losing a historical opportunity, as happened in the case of Cyprus in 2004, the Georgian society should carefully study the accumulated international experience in this direction and draw relevant conclusions.

According to all of the above, we consider it an urgent necessity for the Georgian side to take an active initiative and find a platform where Georgians, Abkhazians, and Ossetians can start relations, restore trust, and build peace; otherwise, every inactive day is a big loss.

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